

EXPLORING THE LEXICAL AND STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES OF DEPED MEMOS

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ABSTRACT

A memorandum is a short notice usually written by the management to address a certain policy or give a certain announcement or changes in an organization. Thus, this paper aims to identify the structural and lexical properties of the Department of Education memoranda. The paper used the discourse analysis type of research and the memoranda from August to December 2018, which were posted on the Department of Education website and served as the study's corpus. It was found that the DepEd memos used simple, direct words and no abbreviations. Simple sentences were also used in making the memorandum. On the structural properties, it was found out that DepEd memos the words in the memorandum are specific and direct to the point to facilitate better understanding among the readers. It could be further observed that the words used are not abbreviated instead it is spelled out and it also contains an explanatory note of what the memo is all about. On its lexical properties, the memorandum uses performative verbs to set that the tone of the memorandum is prescriptive as its goal is to direct or call for action among the employees of the department. In terms of resemblance between a legal letter and a memorandum, DepEd memorandum and legal letters have a resemblance to one another as they are crafted like communication letters which have receiver and signatories on them, words are direct to the point and they use also performative verbs.

Keywords: *structural properties, lexical properties, memorandum, discourse analysis, legal letters*

INTRODUCTION

Language is important for people as they use it as a source of expressing their ideas and emotions to people. It comes into two types: written and spoken Mashuri (2011), asserts that language as a medium of communication has two types, there are written and spoken. Spoken language can be realized in oration, dialogue, and presentation. Meanwhile, written language can be realized in letters, news, short message, short story, and novel. Spoken language means that language is expressed in speaking whereas, written language is the language expressed in writing. Communication in written language as people know is a text.

One example of a written language is a memorandum. Memoranda are written with the purpose of commanding a person to do something. ResearchGuide would point out that a memorandum is a short notice usually written by the management to address a certain policy or give a certain announcement or changes in an organization. In the Department of Education, memos are made to command their personnel to do a task or to follow a certain order which they are required to do as a public servant. Every form of correspondence has a definite language used to make sure that they are going to be understood by the people who will be reading it. In writing, your main goal is to be understood by the readers thus appropriate language should be considered in writing.

In the article, Gannage (1999), argued that a well-organized memorandum conveys a lucid, methodical way of thinking about the problem. A well-written memorandum should have a clear message to the readers wherein they will be called to do an action or to follow an order. ResearchGuide point out also that in writing a good memo it should be short as possible, use simple English, use captivating heading, and avoid simple grammar and spelling.

There were no researches that were conducted on the properties of a memorandum. On the other hand, in the study of Mashuri (2011), conducted a study on the genre moves different memorandum of understanding taken from 5 different learning institutions. He found out that the social function of a memorandum of understanding is to inform and describe an agreement between parties with several terms conditions and. The difference lies only in the scope of the program. Furthermore, he found out that there are five processes that occur in the memorandum and these are: material process, mental process, verbal process, relational process, and existential process, and all the clauses used declarative mood type.

On the other hand, in the study conducted by de Maria (2003), wherein he made a contrastive analysis of the transmittal letter and memoranda both in English and Spanish, he found out that all letters and memos examined (109) both in Spanish and English presented a common and constant movement in their generic structure: the transmittal move which constituted the obligatory move. It was also found that the request move was the most frequent optional one. Although in not large percentages, it appeared in English letters (43.7%), in English memos (31.%), in Spanish letters (24.2%), and in Spanish memos (21%). Memos in both English and Spanish presented a very low percentage of optional moves. These moves were information, instruction, and thankfulness. The sample was widely dispersed. Thus, it was difficult to obtain a definite pattern regarding optional moves. Similarly, letters in both languages had the same problem. The optional moves that presented a low percentage of frequency in Spanish and English letters were commitment, instruction, justification, clarification, and description. While in Spanish memos and letters, the writer involves himself, in English, this does not occur. In

Spanish transmittal documents, the writer uses the first person singular or plural when announcing the sending of a document. For example: “Me permito enviar ...” or “Estamos anexando...” In English, the writer frequently uses the imperative which becomes an instruction. For example: “Please find attached...”. We can also observe that this instruction is accompanied by a courteous expression.

In the study of Madrunio (2022), wherein she studied the lexical and grammatical features of a memorandum of agreement, she found that MOAs are characterized by linguistic features to accomplish certain functions. Seven out of the 11 linguistic features abound in the local MOAs, and these are binomial expressions, generic/cognitive structuring, legal archaisms, modality, negators, sentence length and complexity, and specialized, distinctive, and technical legal lexis. For international MOAs, there are only four out of the 11 features found to be notable. These are generic/cognitive structuring, modality, negators, and sentence length and complexity.

Moreover, the study by Pengsun & Yushan (2014) concluded that the three main process types occurring most often in the legal memorandum are material, relational, and mental processes, in which the material process far outnumbers the other two. The messages conveyed in the legal memorandum are stated objectively. The material, relational choices of clauses represent the scenery vividly and therefore constitute powerful evidence. A mental process may weaken this effect or even threaten to make people doubt the facts presented. Secondly, the most common practice is to apply nouns or nominal phrases, or even normalization elements to be the subject of a legal memorandum. The employment of the Present tense is always for the finite. Concerning the residue in mood structure, predicator is present in all major clauses. Complement, an element in residue, could be lifted out of the adjunct to become subject in certain circumstances. The modal adjunct and conjunctive adjuncts play a significant role in the density of the discourse and the intensity of the coherence. From the perspective of the mood function of the clause, declarative and imperative clauses are typical sentence patterns in legal memorandum. Where information is offered or the situation is explained, a legal memorandum is often applied in legal English. The declarative clauses are mainly used to fulfill the communicative purpose of informing, so it is commonly adopted in the moves Statement of Facts, Discussion, and Finis. Imperative or command sentence regulating prohibitions and obligations is typically used to perform the legal directives. Lastly, the multiple theme and the clausal theme are the distinctive features used in the legal memorandum. The author found that the written language uses rich but standard vocabulary, simple sentence structure of some variety, densely complex phrases, and fewer adjectival modifiers. On the other hand, two kinds of structure can be seen. One is the syntax where the subject is omitted. The other is the syntax of a phrase rather than a sentence, which may be a prepositional phrase, a noun phrase, or a verb phrase. In the text, it should be better to spell out a number to begin a sentence so that the whole demonstration is carried out in a well-organized process. Furthermore, all good English legal memorandums are observed to possess four basic characteristics which can be briefly described as accuracy, clarity, simplicity, and concision.

This paper aimed to determine the structural and lexical properties of the DepEd memo and to determine whether these memoranda have a close resemblance to the legal letters. Furthermore, the corpus of the study is the DepEd memoranda which can be found on the Department of Education website which has 5,000 words. It only focused on the structural and lexical properties of the memoranda.

Research Questions

The study determined the lexical and structural properties of DepEd memos.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How are the DepEd memos are constructed?
 2. What are the lexical and structural properties of DepEd memoranda?
 3. How do the DepEd memoranda closely resemble legal letters in terms of their lexical and structural properties?
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METHODOLOGY

The study made use of the descriptive- qualitative type and discourse analysis types of research. The data that were used in the study are the department memorandum from the Department of Education. In analyzing the data, the researcher first downloaded the department memorandum from the DepEd website, next, the researcher analyzed the data by using the study of Berukstiene on the properties of legal texts as his basis. After analyzing the data, the researchers would be able to identify the structural and lexical properties of the memorandum in the Department of Education.

RESULTS

The following are the results of the study:

1. DepEd memoranda, simple and direct words were used to facilitate better understanding. there were no abbreviations found in the corpus thus, it can come to the conclusion that the memoranda are in the formal language as this would affirm that a memorandum is a written communication that intends to direct or to inform people.
 2. In terms of structural properties, the words in the memorandum are specific and direct to the point to facilitate better understanding among the readers. In terms of lexical properties, the memorandum uses performative verbs such as: may, are enjoined, are encouraged, are required, are authorized to attend, are advised, is desired, shall deliver, shall be charged, is directed to submit, shall be allowed, are requested, shall conduct, and others.
 3. In both legal letters and the DepEd memorandum, words are direct to the point and they use also performative verbs, but legal letters are more directive and compelling in the words they use. Both of these also are crafted like letters wherein they contain the receiver and signatories.
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DISCUSSION

On the words used in constructing the memorandum and how was it constructed?

In terms of words used in the DepEd memoranda, simple and direct words were used to facilitate better understanding. Furthermore, there were no abbreviations found in the corpus thus, it can come to the conclusion that the memoranda are in the formal language as this would affirm that a memorandum is a written communication that intends to direct or to inform people.

At the end of the memorandum, there is this word “Immediate dissemination of this memorandum is desired”- from this line, it could be seen that the memorandum is made to direct or to command people to respond on the matter that is being discussed in the memo. Aside from its directs, the memorandum cannot command or direct without telling or explaining what the memorandum is all about and this could be found in the first part of the memorandum. It would not be called a memo if there is no explanation of what is all about. This introductory part already informs the people of what it is all about. “The Department of Education announces the results of the 2018 Schools Division Superintendent Examination otherwise known as the Educational Management Test (EMT) which was administered on February 25, 2018, at the Makati Science High School, Kalayaan Avenue, Makati City.” From this line, it can be seen that the memo is all about the announcement of the successful examinees of the Educational Management Test.

In terms of the sentences, simple sentences were employed in crafting this kind of communication letter to facilitate better understanding among the readers as this kind of communication letter is to inform and direct. An example would be: “The winners in the 17th PRO will represent the Philippine Robotics Team in the World Robot Olympiad 2018 from November 15 to 19, 2018 in Chiang Mai, Thailand. Aside from that, compound and complex sentences were used also, especially in the first and second parts as those parts would explain what is the memo all about. It also gives information to the readers and an example would be: “The Felta Multi-Media Inc., in collaboration with the Department of Education, will conduct the following activities of the 17th Philippine Robotics Olympiad (PRO) for the school year 2018-2019.” and “The official participants from each region at the national level Deped-BCD STF shall only be the Rank 1 Regional Winners in each of the different categories, whose entries have been approved by the national level Scientific Review Committee (SRC).

On the structural and lexical properties of the memoranda

In terms of structural properties, the words in the memorandum are specific and direct to the point to facilitate better understanding among the readers. It could further be observed that the words used are not abbreviated instead it is spelled out but in some cases, the memorandum uses an abbreviation so as not to make the memorandum redundant regarding a certain activity such as in this line: “All schools, school district offices, SDOs, ROs and CO are required to post streamers with the required logo to ensure that the public is aware of the NTM, NTD and WTD celebrations.” An example would be: “The deadline for filing of application is on September 7, 2018, while the examination will be conducted on October 21, 2018.”- from this given example it could be observed that it is direct to the point by just informing the said activity. Moreover, the memorandum is not complete without any explanation of what the memo is all about; thus in every first part of it, there is an explanation that summarizes the whole point of the memo. With these kinds of words that they use, a memorandum is both descriptive as it tries to describe a said activity and prescriptive as it orders or directs the people to follow the said order as such in this line: “All schools, school district offices, SDOs, Ros, and CO are required to post streamers with the required logo to ensure that the public is aware of the NTM, NTD, and WTD celebrations.” Another prominent feature that could be found on the memorandum is the receiver as it would tell the names of the person to whom the memo is addressed and the last part is always the person to which the memo came from. If the memo is all about activities or contests, there is always a focal person that can be contacted wherein it states the position and the number of the person. An example would be: “For more information, contact Ms. Anna Liza M. Chan, Senior Education Program Specialist, BCD- Curriculum Standards Development Division (CSDD). Department of Education (DepEd) Central Office, 3rd Floor Bonifacio Building, DepEd Complex,

Meralco Avenue, Pasig City at telephone nos. (02) 632-7746 and (02) 635-9822, or email at nstf@deped.gov.ph.

In terms of lexical properties, the memorandum uses performative verbs such as: may, are enjoined, are encouraged, are required, are authorized to attend, are advised, is desired, shall deliver, shall be charged, is directed to submit, shall be allowed, are requested, shall conduct, and others. The use of these verbs sets that the tone of the memorandum is prescriptive as its goal is to direct or call for action among the employees of the department. Furthermore, word choice here are words that could be understood by the employees of the Department of Education as it talks about education, programs of the department, and the learners. Even though it is performative in nature, the words are just more gentle as compared to legal texts.

On the close resemblance of the DepEd memo to the legal letters in terms of its structural and lexical properties

The legal letters in terms of structural properties are direct to the point but it is formulaic and stereotypical since they are intended for legal terminology; in terms of lexical properties it uses Latinisms, terminologies, and the use of performative verbs but the words here are more compelling as compared to the memorandum.

On the DepEd memorandum, in terms of structural properties, it is direct to the point and the majority of the sentences that were used are simple sentences and in terms of lexical properties it uses also performative verbs but these are more gentle as compared to legal letters.

In both legal letters and the DepEd memorandum, words are direct to the point and they use also performative verbs; but legal letters are more directive and compelling in the words they used. Both of these also are crafted like letters wherein they contain the receiver and signatories.

Conclusions

DepEd memorandum just like any communication letter has also structural and lexical properties. In structural properties, words are direct to the point and they seldom use abbreviations because words are spelled out properly. It also contains an introductory part to explain what the memorandum is all about. And in lexical properties, it also uses performative verbs to direct and instruct its employees. DepEd memorandum and legal letters have a resemblance to one another as they are crafted like communication letters which have receiver and signatories on them, words are direct to the point and they use also performative verbs.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. Further study should be conducted along memoranda not only focusing on the Department of Education but also on other agencies as well.
 2. A study of the same kind is also possible as long as it includes a wider scope such as the expansion of years that need to be included in the corpus of the study.
 3. Further study on the other types of written communication along with their structural and lexical properties should be done to have a wider scope of knowledge.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study is purely qualitative in nature and no human respondents were used in the study; thus, there is no harm or risk. With regard to its credibility, the author religiously cited authors with whom he borrowed ideas in the study. The interpretation is purely done by the researcher and it was validated by her colleagues in the academe. The purpose of the study is a requirement for one of the researcher's subjects in his doctorate study.

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